

www.arseam.com

IMPLEMENTATION OF CMNAVIGO, A MANUFACTURING EXECUTION SYSTEM (MES) AT INDASA ABRASIVE INDUSTRIES

Tulika Chakravorty

Doctoral Scholar,
Logistics and Supply Chain Management,
University of Petroleum & Energy Studies
(UPES) , Dehradun, Uttaranchal.

Dr. Samyadip Chakraborty*

Assistant Professor,
Dept. of Operations & IT
IBS Hyderabad, IFHE University,
Hyderabad, Telangana

Abstract:

Objective- This is a teaching case, which is developed based on secondary facts and figures available in public domain, aimed at illustrating importance of Information Systems (IS) in a business context. The case is about a business (the company name is INDASA which is situated in Portugal and is a well known face in Portuguese abrasive industry) that wants to gain an edge in global markets. The company is facing plethora of problems like high labor cost, single factory meeting the needs of worldwide supplies, etc. This case portrays the journey of INDASA through the implementation of its new IS platform (cmNavigo). This case gradually builds up the problem by carefully guiding the journey from the beginning of the millennium to early 2012 and lists the major factors affecting it. The case also highlights the various challenges and alternatives that Indasa have in hand and finally carefully analyzes the alternatives and how the implementation of the IS platform has bring about the changes in the firms bottom-line figures has been contrasted with previous year findings/figures.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present article is based on secondary facts and figures collected from open-source and public domain. This case is written in typical teaching case style and format where chronologically the problem formulation, discussion, analysis and result stages have been carved out.

Findings- Effective implementation of manufacturing execution system (cmNavigo) has been linked with efficient and sustainable growth and better sales figures. This study is based on secondary data and hence needs no further validation.

Practical implications-This paper can inspire managers and experts in manufacturing sector under similar business backdrop and give them inspiration and motivation, rather better insight in terms of what is the right way and right time for implementing information system and also help

them understand a lot of linked whys and hows. However caution should be followed because case by case analysis and detailed understanding of the situation should be antecedent to this step before indiscriminate copying of the said model as described in the case. Moreover further authentication based on primary data from similar firm-specific example might make the managerial understanding more robust.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical real-life case based findings and situations which makes the entire learning effort more understandable and interesting for both academics as well as the industry managers.

Key words: Information Systems, Manufacturing execution system, Case study.

“Europe’s strength as a production location is based on the power of innovation, engineering skills and in the quality of skilled labor resources. In order to compensate for the higher labor expenses, European manufacturers need optimal and highly automated production processes”

- Hans Mayer, COO of znt GmbH

“Critical Manufacturing’s flagship product cmNavigo continues to be the leading innovative Manufacturing Execution System for high-tech industries. It takes advantage of the integration, interoperability and feature rich Microsoft technology stack that enables a state-of-the-art user experience, world class performance and scalability coupled with a low total cost of ownership”

- João Cortez, Product Manager, Critical Manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

In late 2012, INDASA -Indústria de Abrasivos, S. A. selected two firms PT Prime¹& Critical Manufacturing², to implement cmNavigo, a Manufacturing Execution System (MES)³ at their

¹ PT Prime is an IT & Engineering services firm owned by Portugal Telecom.

² Critical Manufacturing is a spin-off company of Critical Software. It specializes mainly in manufacturing systems and automation. (Wikipedia, n.d)

new factory located in Aviero, Portugal⁴. This was the first time that cmNavigo was being implemented in Portugal.

cmNavigo, as a software package was developed by Critical Manufacturing, a firm based in Portugal. Speaking about Critical Manufacturing's status as a Gold member in the Microsoft partner network⁵, Adélio Fernandes, Critical Manufacturing's VP for Technology stated, *“Critical Manufacturing is very pleased to, once again, have its technical competences recognized within the demanding requirements of the Microsoft Partner Network. Being part of this restricted group provides guarantees to our customers regarding the knowledge and support for Microsoft products and technologies”*⁶.

Though Critical Manufacturing has a rich experience in developing software to assist manufacturing processes, the firm has little experience in system integration. Since a contract requires both system integration and software implementation, Critical Manufacturing had to partner with a local firm that specializes in system integration, in whichever country it intended to sell its product. For example, it partnered with zntRichter for the distribution of cmNavigo in the countries of Austria, Germany and Switzerland⁷.

BACKGROUND NOTE

Founded in 1979, INDASA - Indústria de Abrasivos is currently the leading European firm in the production of flexible abrasives⁸ specially designed for use in automotive refinishing. The firm has its central location in Aviero, Portugal. INDASA is known for having implemented some of the most modernized manufacturing processes in abrasive manufacturing. The INDASA group

³Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) are computerized systems used in manufacturing that work in real time to enable the control of multiple elements of the production process

⁴pr.com, 2013

⁵Microsoft Partner Network or MPN is Microsoft Inc.'s partner network designed to make resources available to a wide variety of technology companies so they can build a business around Microsoft technologies. (Wikipedia, n.d)

⁶Critical Manufacturing S.A, 2012

⁷znt Richter, 2011

⁸ An Abrasive is a hard material that is used to machine, grind, or finish a workpiece. (Tooling University, n.d)

has expanded vastly over the globe with its platform locations in Spain, United Kingdom, France, Germany, Poland, Brazil and USA.

Since its inception, the firm has always concentrated heavily in the implementation of new technologies in manufacturing and automation. This strategy was perfectly in line with the firm's goal of maintaining International quality standards. In the year 2000, INDASA was certified ISO 9001 in the development, production and distribution of flexible abrasives⁹. This quality, combined with the firm's emphasis on R&D has made it a leader in the abrasives market. Also due to this emphasis on quality standards, INDASA was also able to mark a global presence. In November 2011, INDASA was awarded the "Best SME exporter of tradable goods", an award that had over 2000 contestants¹⁰.

In 2012, INDASA formulated a 20-year growth plan, with the main intention of tapping the International markets¹¹. Since INDASA was already maintaining International quality standards, the main threat for the firm in the international markets was price competition. INDASA being in Europe (characterized by high labor costs), had to compete with global abrasive giants that had factories located in countries with low cost of labor. The firm needed a way to leverage both quality and price. As a part of its 20-year growth strategy, INDASA opened a new factory in 2012. Through this facility the firm was expecting to "step-up" its production levels.

THE NEED

Based on the 20-year growth strategy, INDASA formulated its year-by-year growth plans. In this process, the management noticed three main concerns for INDASA. The first concern was size. The size of the company both in terms of the facilities and employees was to increase rapidly. Would it be able to exercise the control over its inputs in an efficient way like before? Would the firm's existing production control system be sufficient to ensure this level of efficiency? Also, as a general principle, as the size of the firm goes on increasing, the ability of the ERP (by itself) to handle the large number of processes goes on falling.

⁹Indasa Abrasive Industries, 2000

¹⁰Indasa Abrasive Industries, 2011

¹¹Indasa Abrasive Industries, 2012

The second concern was change. The growth plan involved a high degree of technological transformation, which meant that there was a strong chance of changing job designs in the future. Would it be able to make the system more “operationally comfortable” for the employees who were used to working on older equipment? Can the organization transform its production process without having any negative impacts?

The third and the most important concern was quality. Customer expectations in terms of both higher quality and lower prices were rising in the abrasive markets. Also, since INDASA’s long term strategy involved foray into the foreign markets, international quality standards had to be met. INDASA needed a system that, while being cost-effective, would ensure a high quality of production. These three concerns pointed INDASA’s management towards cmNavigo, a Manufacturing Execution system (MES) developed by Critical Manufacturing. The contract was awarded and critical manufacturing was to implement cmNavigo in collaboration with PT Prime.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MES

Being experienced in MES implementation, the project team from PT prime was aware of the potential problems in change management. So right after it established the MES requirements and decided on the implementation schedule, it formed a team of INDASA employees spanning all functionalities and levels of management. The first meeting involved a briefing of the changes that the firm will be going through.

The first process that the project team from PT Prime concentrated on, was manufacturing process governance. In this phase various authority-related information was collected. The main pieces of information collected were, “For a particular manufacturing process, which particular employees are authorized to change the process?”, “Who has to approve the change in that process?” and “What is the hierarchy of approvals that the change must pass through before it is implemented in the system?”.

The next step was Data migration¹². An MES implementation required the data to be made “centrally available”. For this, first the minimum amount and types of data that were needed for the effective implementation of the MES were identified. Then, the primary sources of these data were identified. Once the visibility in the data was achieved, the team developed the migration code and tested it on a few samples. Once these steps were completed, the final migration code was run and the data was extracted and loaded into the new system after performing some predetermined transformations.

The next step was the Integration of the system with the shop floor equipment. This was deemed as the most complex and daunting step in the implementation process. The shop floor equipment were not only separate from the ERP, but were also separate from each other. To achieve integration, the different manufacturing systems had to be first integrated into the MES and then the MES had to be integrated with the ERP. The main challenge here was that there was a “loose handshake” between the shop floor equipment and cmNavigo. The integration points between different systems were identified and the standardized interfaces were defined and then implemented. For example, the ASRS (Automatic Storage and Retrieval System)¹³ was no longer a standalone system. It was now integrated with the MES and all the ASRS-related information would be easily accessible through the cmNavigo’s interface. cmNavigo would also enable the control of the ASRS. Also, earlier the equipment had its own embedded software and when required, the operator had to separately report the equipment related information such as outage, output, load factors etc. through a separate Information system. After integration, the information related to the shop floor equipment could be viewed on cmNavigo’s interface by the concerned managers.

The next step was integration of the ERP with the MES. The project team stated its aim in this phase as, “*what the production facility must produce, must be told to the MES by the ERP. Then, the MES should tell the ERP what it has done and what it is doing*”. Experts from General Electric were known to say, “*ERP systems know what customers want, and MES systems know*

¹²“Data Migration is the process of moving data from one or more sources into a target application” (Sphata Systems, n.d)

¹³“An Automated storage and retrieval system (ASRS or AS/RS) consists of a variety of computer-controlled systems for automatically placing and retrieving loads from defined storage locations” (Wikipedia, n.d)

how to build it.”During this phase, the team ensured strict compliance with the ISA-95¹⁴ systems integration standard. The ERP integration was performed as planned and a complete shop-floor equipment-MES-ERP integration was achieved.

The next step was cmNavigo software configuration and Installation in different systems. During this phase, the software was configured to match INDASA’s requirements and was installed in the different computers at INDASA. Standard templates for dashboards were also created for the managers to choose from.

The final step of the implementation process was software deployment¹⁵ and provision of go-live support¹⁶ for the new system. Since the factory followed the continuous production system (24 hours a day, 7 days a week), an integrated test was not possible without an outage. Also, all along the MES implementation process the project team was preparing the MES training curriculum in parallel. Critical manufacturing had a standardized training curriculum for cmNavigo, which was modified to suit the client’s needs. Also a permanent cmNavigo simulator was built, to assist employee training without any interruption to the manufacturing process. Employees were required to train themselves through the curriculum besides giving multiple tests on the simulator, to get certified. cmNavigo then stored this information for the operational managers to view the cmNavigo proficiency levels of different operators. The system also had capabilities of storing data about other certifications.

¹⁴“ISA-95 is the international standard for the integration of enterprise and control systems” (isa95.com, n.d)

¹⁵Software deployment is the process of getting a program ready for its intended use.

¹⁶ Go-live support is the making available of the additional resources that will be required to support the activation of any new system.

BENEFITS ACHIEVED

Through the implementation of the MES, INDASA now has an integrated system for its manufacturing facility. Compared to the previous systems that it used, the new system was advanced in terms of technology, speed and ease of control. The different production processes were now more visible as cmNavigo enabled an “interactive top view” of the different processes. These top views showed the equipment status (up or down) with the actual layout.

Exhibit II

Screenshot of cmNavigo showing Total visibility and control of the production lines with layout-based interactivity

Since the production control was integrated with the ERP, order management was more efficient. Every time an order for more than a predetermined quantity was received, the ERP initiated changes in the inventory management system and alerted the MES to step-up the production. This increased the system's ability to cater to fluctuating demand. The new system also enabled the operators to view spare part availability, enabling quick decision making during equipment downtime. There was also a feature of storing the images of different equipment faults with information about the specific fault. This enabled the equipment operators to quickly diagnose the cause for equipment failure and initiate the maintenance process without having to wait for the maintenance personnel.

Touch screen interfaces were installed at shop floor workstations which enabled two-way communications between the shop floor personnel and their managers. One main benefit here was the use of decision trees. Operational managers specified decision trees for routine structured problems in the system. The shop floor personnel could just view the decision tree and make the decision instead of waiting for the concerned manager to make the decision. This not only saved time, but also expanded the job descriptions of the concerned shop floor personnel by giving them more decision making powers. Operators could also view the equipment and the MES documentation on their touch-screen panels.

For managers, cmNavigo enabled a better visual management of different KPI's that they preferred to monitor such as Count¹⁷, Target¹⁸,Reject ratio/rate¹⁹, takt time²⁰, Overall Equipment effectiveness(OEE)²¹ etc. cmNavigo also had OLAP and data mining capabilities. The managers could customize the different dimensions across which they wished to view data, and cmNavigo would perform the slicing & dicing operations, and present the data in a “visible form”. cmNavigo also enabled generation of exception reports. Different managers could specify various deviation protocols based on different KPI's and they would be alerted on their respective dashboards every time a KPI deviated from its normal range.

¹⁷ Count is a statistic that shows that shows the number of defective units in random sample audits (usually out of 100).

¹⁸ Manufacturing Target is the number of units that a manufacturing unit aims at manufacturing in a particular time period. (per-day basis in this case)

¹⁹ Reject Ratio or rejection rate is the ratio or percentage of the number of rejected (based on tolerance levels) units in a certain number of processed units.

²⁰“Takt Time is the rate that a completed product needs to be finished in order to meet customer demand” (isixsigma, n.d)

²¹“In Manufacturing, OEE is a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) calculated based on the three OEE Factors: Availability, Performance, and Quality” (oeecom, n.d)

FUTURE BENEFITS

The main intention for INDASA's management in choosing cmNavigo was the flexibility and scalability features that the software offered. INDASA is currently in the second year of its 20-year growth plan. There would be a lot of changes occurring in the firm's production facilities in the upcoming years. cmNavigo was designed to accommodate such changes.

Based on INDASA's focus on growth, one of the changes the firm will be going through, is the addition of new work flows and changing of existing work flows. cmNavigo has its own tool called fablive to add new workflows and change the existing ones. This is the prime flexibility feature of the software.

The implementation of cmNavigo at INDASA has provided ease of control & management, and flexibility that the firm would need, to execute its 20-year growth strategy. The MES has also enabled a cost-effective way of producing high quality abrasives in large quantities, something that most European manufacturers aspire for.

Exhibit - VII

Features of cmNavigo – I

Feature	Description
Materials & container	Multi-level, automation ready material & position controlled container models.
Resource tracking	Multi-level clustered resources. Multiple user-defined state-models
Durables & consumables management	Associate durables with resources. Track while enforcing expiration dates.
Routing & dispatching	Hierarchical flows with optional steps & rework paths.
BOM	Assembly transactions, BOM's and Consumables. Automatic consumption
Order management	Plan, manage and track production orders
Data collection	Advanced data collection, with limits, samples & calculations. Immediate, Long-running;.
Statistical process control	Variable & attribute charts, integrated with data collection and exceptions . Western Electric and user defined SPC rules.
Exceptions & checklists	User defined deviation protocols, with checklists , integrated with SPC, Data Collection and material tracking
Specification management	Master data management, including change management of versioned objects with custom approval loops
Maintenance management	Integrated ad-hoc, time and usage based maintenance management. Spare parts inventory management. Hold equipment after late due.

Source: cmNavigo Brochure

Exhibit – VII (contd.)

Features of cmNavigo – II

Feature	Description
Recipe management	Hierarchical parameterized recipes. Recipe resolution. Dynamic parameter calculation Integrated with Material and Resource Tracking
fablive	Compose a real fab layout and monitor the equipment status in real time.
Dashboards	User-defined dashboards composed by customizable graphical widgets
Electronic failure catalogue	Store a visual catalogue of failures and pick failures out of an image.
Documentation management	Create, updated, publish and view documents with notifications and integrated with change control. Associate and visualize documents with material and resource contexts
Costing	Track material costs in real time as costs are incurred during processing. Report material inventory cost, material cost history and standard product cost.
Certification management	Management of users and their skills. Grant and revoke certifications. Certification expiration. Validate skills in some operations.
Advanced layout & printing	Define and print labels and lot travellers based on MES dynamic information.
GUI, object and api level security	Restrict access to any GUI element, any object or any API.
Reporting and OLAP	Advanced Custom Reports. OLAP slicing & dicing operations on a Data warehouse
Data Mining	Advanced data mining algorithms and analysis.
ERP integration	Flexible ERP integration with native support for SAP.
Equipment integration	Multiple interfaces, allow full integration with cmNavigo.

Source: cmNavigo Brochure

References

1. Critical Manufacturing and PT Have Been Selected for a cmNavigo Implementation at Indasa - PR.com. 2013. Critical Manufacturing and PT Have Been Selected for a cmNavigo Implementation at Indasa - PR.com. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.pr.com/press-release/471580>.
2. Microsoft Partner Ecosystem - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. 2013. Microsoft Partner Ecosystem - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. [ONLINE] Available at: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microsoft_Partner_Ecosystem.
3. Critical Manufacturing cmNavigo. 2011. Critical Manufacturing cmNavigo. [ONLINE] Available at: http://www.znt-richter.com/cmnavigo_en/. [:: Indasa :: - The Company . 2013. :: Indasa :: - The Company. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.INDASA.pt/gca/?id=40>.
4. :: Indasa :: Quality and Environment . 2000. :: Indasa :: Quality and Environment. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.INDASA.pt/gca/?id=44>.
5. Critical Manufacturing renews Microsoft's Gold Certification status. 2012. Critical Manufacturing renews Microsoft's Gold Certification status. [ONLINE] Available at: http://www.criticalmanufacturing.com/newsroom/press_releases/2012/9/MS_Gold_2012
6. INDASA awarded prize for best SME exporter. 2011. INDASA awarded prize for best SME exporter. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.INDASA.pt/noticias/detalhes.php?id=9>
7. INDASA invests in innovation and technological development processes to ensure a more sustainable and competitive in international markets. 2013. INDASA invests in innovation and technological development processes to ensure a more sustainable and competitive in international markets. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.INDASA.pt/noticias/detalhes.php?id=9>
8. Sphata Systems Data Migration - Sphata Systems. n.d. Sphata Systems Data Migration - Sphata Systems. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.sphata.com/services/data-migration/>.
9. Automated storage and retrieval system - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. N.d. Automated storage and retrieval system - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. [ONLINE] Available at: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Automated_storage_and_retrieval_system.
10. Integrating Your ERP and MES to Improve Operations. N.d. GE Intelligence Platforms. [ONLINE] Available at: http://leadwise.mediadroit.com/files/9021integrating_erp_and_mes_wp_gft763.pdf.
11. ISA-95 | ISA-95 is the international standard for the integration of enterprise and control systems ISA-95. N.d. ISA-95 | ISA-95 is the international standard for the integration of enterprise and control systems ISA-95. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.isa-95.com/>.

12. Takt Time. 2013.n.d.Takt Time. [ONLINE] Available at:
<http://www.isixsigma.com/dictionary/takt-time/>.
13. Calculating OEE Overall Equipment Effectiveness. N.d. Calculating OEE Overall
Equipment Effectiveness. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.oee.com/calculating-oee.html>.